

BEST PRACTICES FOR MONITORING GRADE INFLATION

ABSTRACT: Alleged grade inflation could make it challenging for students to even get into university programs in the Middle East. Are academic institutions in Saudi Arabia inflating their grades? From extra credit assignments to challenges with grade distributions, multiple factors are considered to be suspects of skewing student achievement results at educational institutions around the world. Higher education institutions experiencing problems can utilize a research-based survey included in this article and other resources, such as international accreditation procedures, to address curriculum challenges. This paper provides recommendations to monitor grade inflation (on program and course levels) and to stimulate research contributions on this topic from the Middle East in international journals.

INTRODUCTION

Grade inflation is a problem at universities across the globe (McAllister, Jian, & Aghazadeh, 2008; Felton & Koper, 2005; Fajardo, 2004; Martinson, 2004; Cushman, 2003; Kfir, Fresko, & Benjamin-Paul, 2002). Academics have criticized or supported grade inflation procedures at their respective universities in popular education media (e.g., *Chronicle in Higher Education*; *Time Education Supplement*). Some have also analyzed data across institutions and recommended procedures to ratify grade inflation in academic journals. Some academic institutions have also ignored the grade inflation issue (ASHE, 2005). Overall, Australian, British, Canadian, and American universities have documented grade inflation in well-known academic journals but there were not any studies published in English about universities in the Middle East.

For example, North American Universities have witnessed a significant increase in grade point averages in the past 30 years (Rojstaker, 2002; Astin, 1998 found in German & Scandura, 2005; Edwards, 2000). It is imperative for administrators to develop a balanced approach to monitoring grade inflation which recognizes students' achievements, respects the academic freedom of faculty members, and helps improve the quality of education at their

institutions (Kfir, Fresko, & Benjamin-Paul, 2002). Identifying the best practices in monitoring [regulating, managing, and controlling] grade inflation at higher education institutions around the world and how the practices might be used in the Middle East are the goals of this article.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Mullen (1995) defined grade inflation in that it is "when a grade is viewed as being less rigorous than it ought to be" (p.29). Several studies reviewed cited grade inflation examples from two of the top American Universities- Harvard and Princeton. In 1966, 22% of Harvard's undergraduates earned A's (Mullen, 1995) and increased to 46% by 1996 (Mullen, 1995). Also, 82% of Harvard seniors in 1996 also graduated with honors (Mullen, 1995). In 1973, 31% Princeton's undergraduates earned A's and increased to 43% by 1997 (Rosovsky & Hartley, 2002). Notably, only 12% of all grades given at Princeton were below a B (Rosovsky & Hartley, 2002). Were the students at Harvard, or Princeton, smarter than the average student at other universities or were professors too lenient in grading? Douthat (2005) suggested Harvard students simply knew how to select "easy" courses, and literature art professors failed to reinforce major courses with challenging materials. Regardless of the absolute cause, these top American universities, with

supposedly the highest educational standards, found grade inflation and have attempted to counterbalance the abnormal distribution of grades.

For example, Aronauer (2005) reported that the number of A's given at Princeton University in 2004-2005 had decreased from previous years (i.e. 46 percent received A's in 2003-2004 versus 40.9 percent in 2004-2005). This reduction was attributed to a plan developed by the Dean of Princeton's undergraduate college in April of 2004 where only 35 percent of the grades in undergraduate courses could be A's and only 55 percent for independent research projects. Modifications can be made and the number of A's can decrease, as what occurred at Princeton, but is counting A's the way to assure the quality of education and that the standards are comparable to other institutions? These research articles suggest different types of institutions may require other types of monitoring methods, especially international higher education institutions. The following sections discuss various causes and effects of grade inflation as well as research-based solutions for higher education institutions.

What are the alleged causes of grade inflation?

Student Evaluations

One of the most common grade inflation factors known is faculty members not wanting to get low student evaluations (German & Scandura, 2005; Gordon, 2005). Institutions which emphasize student evaluations will most likely find professors who get the highest evaluations will also tend to give higher grades (Langbein, 2008; Olds & Crumbley, 2003; Yunker & Yunker, 2003; Eiszler, 2002). For example, Eiszler (2002) examined 983,491 student evaluations for 37,000 course sections and found a correlation between the student's expected course grade and ratings of teaching effectiveness.

Kfir, Fresko, Benjamin (2002) found a grade inflation investigation challenges professors' academic freedom. For example, a "hard" professor might feel pressure to "dumb down" their courses if students aren't passing, and an "easy" professor might feel pressure to give lower grades to students just to produce a grade sheet with a bell curve. When expressing pressure to grade easier for higher student evaluations, a professor said "I have not sold my soul to the devil yet, but it's very tempting" ('F' Stands for Feeling the Heat, Graded Instructors Say, 2003).

Assessments

Should faculty help students do better at the end of the term? Based on a study with eleven thousand students (Hassel & Laurey, 2005), grade inflation was attributed to numerous causes including the lack of student responsibility encouraged with extra credit assignments and inconsistency in grade policies. For example, Dowling (2003) highlighted the importance for evaluating procedures to prevent students from cheating and suggested cheating could be a source of grade inflation. Students who are not responsible for their studies may tend to cheat during exams. If assessments are not designed to control cheating (e.g. different versions), students may achieve grades they do not deserve.

Some faculty might also inflate grades because they don't want to decrease students' career and/or higher education opportunities (Gordon, 2005). Do sympathetic professors consider the problems which will occur in their students' professional lives when it is discovered they are actually incompetent? One of the most common ethical violations made by professors is not being prepared for class and giving students' higher grades than they deserved (Bersoff, 2003). Notably, Gordon (2005) found graduate students demonstrate higher performance if they had tough undergraduate courses and felt administrators should go beyond controlling the distribution of grades.

Professional Development & Leadership

Gordon asserted administrators need to increase professor's awareness about grade policies, problems with grade inflation, and best practices in assessing students accurately (Gordon, 2005). Although grade inflation is a much debated issue in the literature, Gordon (2005) found well-known professional associations (e.g., American Council on Education) and institutions have not provided solutions to deter grade inflation. However, the American Psychological Association (APA) has attempted to establish ethical codes that encourages psychologists to only teach courses they are qualified to teach, give fair assessments, and to stay updated in their respective subfields (APA, 2002, Standard 7: Education and Teaching).

Notably, some faculty members have admitted to giving higher grades to avoid angry students (Gordon, 2005) and angry parents (Cook, 2005). Based on observations by Linda Sax, Director of the UCLA Higher Education Research Institute, teachers are pressured to give good grades (Cook, 2005). Most students and even teachers some times tend to forget what the actual grading scale means. Earning a 'C' or 'D' means that the work of the student is average. The problem here is that most students do not know the difference between average, above average, or excellent work. The popular view of grade inflation looks at inflation as being a degradation of academic standards which requires the system to become harder or to raise the standards (grading rubric) (Mansfield, 2001).

Education has moved more towards improving the confidence and self-esteem of the student and one way of doing that is by giving grades that are higher (Fajardo, 2004). However, there needs to be some sort of balance generated in order to allow the standards to be maintained or even improved and still allow for the students to be empowered in the classroom. Fajardo

(2004) argued there needs to be "a return to higher standards, maintaining the core value of academic excellence, and implementing rigor and quality in teaching/learning stand out to be effective ways to curb grade inflation" (p. 73). It is problematic for institutions to assume faculty members, especially those who did not specialize in education or related fields, know how to properly evaluate students. Therefore, institutions must take reasonable steps (e.g. professional development workshops) to ensure students are being evaluated fairly by thoroughly reviewing professors' assessments, evaluation criteria, grade distributions, and even communication skills.

Environmental Factors

Socio-economic factors have historically stimulated academic competition and consequently grade inflation (Gordon, 2005; Boretz, 2004). Some institutions reported grade inflation related to increasing student enrollments required higher standards and hence selected students that perform better than the average student (Gordon, 2005). As a result, Boretz (2004) asserted an ecological approach to grade inflation would consider the fact students who get better grades, will get better educational and professional opportunities.

Boretz (2004) argued grade inflation may at times be the result of better students, better teachers, and better standards at educational institutions. However, educational institutions should regularly document their progress to defend abnormal distributions in their grades. For example, some international accreditation standard processes require teachers to document in their course reports reasons for abnormally high or low grades at least once a year (NCAA, 2005). This information is then summarized in the program reports which are used during institutional reviews. Finally, the information could be used by the rector of a university to make top-level decisions to improve the overall quality of

the institution.

Grades vs. GPAs

In a classic study, Birnbaum (1977) claimed that grade inflation can simply be because student achievement had risen, institutional grading policies allow for student GPAs to increase although the standards for grading have not changed, or demographic factors connected to grading. There should be a distinction between grades rising and GPA's rising (Birnbaum, 1977). When we are reviewing GPA's we are examining grades across a number of courses whereas when looking at a single grade we are examining the level of achievement in a course (Birnbaum, 1977).

Katz (2008) suggested using a different formula to calculate a student's GPA by taking the "standard alpha grades and submit them to two simple formulas, the results of which are then averaged." The process would involve calculating a 'relative grade' for each student in the class as well as the relative rank. Then the two results are averaged which results in the 'composite index' for that class. Once done, then "divide by all credits as per the current system, and the student's overall CI is duly computed" (Katz, 2008).

Goldman (1985) described a shift upwards in a student's GPAs over an extended time period that does not correspond to an increase in student achievement. In contrast, McAllister, Jian, & Aghazadeh (2008) found an increase of A's given to engineering students was related to higher ACT (college entrance exam) scores. Across several institutions differences in grading appear to be related to the characteristics of students changing and in reward structures (Kuh & Hu, 1999). Cook, Butcher, and Raeside (2006) found inadequate controls in subject (or institutional) reviews in the United Kingdom yielded questionable statistical results and education policies (e.g., ranking of universities, funding, etc.). Finally, Glenn (2006) cautioned all responsible

analysts to be careful with reporting erroneous statistics related to grade inflation, and other issues, which have the potential influence of creating misguided education policies.

How can an institution monitor grade inflation?

Based on the literature reviewed, there are several factors that may affect grade inflation such as student evaluations that are connected to performance evaluations of the faculty, competition for students from other institutions, the idea that students are being spoon fed or that the courses are not being taught at an appropriate standard, or higher standards for student enrollment which leads to higher performance. There also various political factors at different institutions which could influence the extent to which academic policies are accepted.

First, it is important for universities to take time to assess the extent to which grade inflation exists by conducting curriculum reviews with local and international institutions. Studies reviewed on grade inflation to systematically investigate student behavior, faculty behavior, and other factors which might have influenced changes in grade distribution ranged from one to eight years (e.g., McAllister, Jian, & Aghazadeh, 2008; Frank & Feeney, 2006; Mulvenon & Ferritor, 2005). Therefore, the monitoring procedures developed at an institution should be periodically implemented over an adequate amount of time before revising policies which can have unintended consequences (e.g., students dropping out, faculty turnover, lower staff morale).

Second, it is important to plan a grade inflation investigation as a component of a larger curriculum/program or institutional review regularly. Once the discussion of grade inflation begins at an institution, monitoring for it and the issues required for accreditation should be completed at four levels (depending on the structure of an

institution): a) course level, b) program level, c) college level, and d) institutional level. The following steps are recommended for quality assurance centers to lead a participatory, empowering, and comprehensive review process:

1. Coordinate Faculty Forum: Quality assurance representatives should invite faculty members to participate in an open discussion about causes of grade inflation. Brainstorming around existing practices (e.g., extra credit) and alternative methods (e.g., increase assessment %) on a particular assignment, could be shared with faculty members in similar subjects. A forum could serve as an opportunity to explore their feelings about potential policies that will be implemented to decrease grade inflation and to discuss political questions. It is important to explore how faculty members use their assessments and the effects of external factors (e.g., national standards) (Bulterman-Bos, Verloop, Terwel, & Wardekker, 2003).

2. Administer Academic Integrity Survey: Based on the results of interviews across departments and/or the faculty forum, factors attributed to grade inflation should be included in a survey in order to summarize institutional and department level perspectives on grade inflation factors. Quality assurance representatives are invited to use and/or modify the enclosed the Academic Integrity Survey for their particular institution (See Appendix A). Thereafter, most of the results should be statistically analyzed as non-parametric data and shared with relevant stakeholders (e.g., deans, department chairs, faculty members, etc.). Once issues are identified, alternative strategies should be considered within the internal and external context of an organization. Previous studies have found faculty perceptions on grade inflation vary (Faculty Perceptions, Reality of Grade Inflation Tell Two Different Stories, 2004; Study Reveals Faculty Attitudes About Grade Inflation, 2004).

3. Complete a SWOT (Strengths,

Weaknesses, Opportunities, & Threat)

Analysis: Focus a SWOT on grade inflation notable effects on the institution and departmental levels. An institution should explore the relationship of their internal system (strengths and weaknesses) with environmental factors (opportunities and threats) which might contribute to grade inflation. After issues relevant to an institutions' structure are reviewed, use the results to design a suitable action plan should be shared in a transparent manner for stakeholders to implement. The action plan should include operationally defining grade inflation based on notable trends. For example, Martinson (2005) recommended questioning how student evaluations are used. Would Edward's (2000) recommendation to institute a peer-evaluation at institutions reduce the impact of grade inflation?

4. Establish Curriculum Review Committee Policies and Procedures:

Conducting curriculum reviews is one method to help benchmark educational standards across other institutions and benchmark relevant policies. However, some institutions fear plagiarism of their course work. Therefore, institution-wide investigations should involve officials aware of institutional planning methods for establishing missions and meeting accreditation standards. For example, the National Commission on Academic Assessment and Accreditation (NCAAA) (2005), requires that institutions should independently verify their standards with other institutions prior to seeking accreditation. Mission statements, accreditation standards, and professional ethics are sources that could be used to reinforce the institutions' commitment to providing a quality education for its students and preserve some notion of academic freedom.

Institutions should regularly update the portfolio for their courses, programs, and institutions to defend the standard of their grading procedures, to affirm the quality of

education their students have received, and defend their faculty members' professionalism to prepare for future international accreditation. For example, professors and administrators should be given support to continuously explore ways to improve the curriculum and assessments for particular courses. Administrators should critique drafts of curriculum review procedures across departments and then establish an institutional policy which covers relevant issues and educational standards (if one doesn't already exist).

5. Forms of Assessment: Is there something about the types of assessments which contributes to more than half of a class getting A's? There are two basic ways of breaking grading down: the bell curve distribution or criterion based. Each program would need to establish guidelines and decisions for how they will go about forms of assessments in their courses. Alternative grading assessments should also be critiqued. Although self-grading (i.e., students evaluating themselves) could increase student motivation and self-concept

(Edwards, 2000), this assessment process could contribute to grade inflation (Strong, Davis, & Hawks, 2004).

Monitoring Model

Once the curriculum review committees are well-established in each department, there should be monitoring on two levels: 1) Program Level 2) Course Level (See Figure 1). Each course represents a small unit within each program. Characteristics of the course learning outcomes, teaching strategies, and assessments are not isolated from the program. Hence, concerns about a course should be investigated holistically in terms of various factors that could contribute to unusual grade distributions (i.e. beyond the instructor's skills). This investigation should be integrated into a comprehensive action plan to hopefully stimulate future research on education systems in the Middle East.

Figure 1: Logic Model for Monitoring Grade Inflation/Curriculum Review Activities

Based on the preliminary analysis on the program and course levels, efforts should be directed to organizing a comprehensive curriculum review across the institution and within the institution to independently verify standards for selected courses. Although such an approach should be built into the departmental strategic plans across programs, information recently requested regarding specific courses establish the need for a broader approach to solving these problems.

Recommendations for monitoring:

Each institution will have their own policies as well as suggestions to help with quality assurance with regards to grade inflation. However, the literature on grade inflation seems to highlight several areas that need to be considered when monitoring for grade inflation. They are: restoration of academic excellence – maintain high academic standards, institutional dialogue, revise the curriculum, transcript should have more information that helps cipher the GPA more appropriately, student evaluations need more thought, and different forms of assessment (Felton & Koper, 2005; Fajardo, 2004; Rosovsky & Hartley, 2002). Based on an assessment of the literature and experience working within various Universities within the Middle East the following are recommended:

- Based on the data available at gradeinflation.com, it is important for any institution to first look at the average GPA for the whole institution from the first year of its inception. Then factors that may have increased or decreased the average GPA should be questioned. Triangulation should be used to investigate trends in courses that might have a significant number of A's or F's. For example, did students in one section consistently perform higher in their other courses? Were there differences in grades between the first and second semesters? Were there any significant

changes to the course (e.g. textbooks or requirements)? Were the books available? Etc.

- As faculty members attempt to increase academic rigor in their courses, management/department chairs should take into consideration faculty members' efforts to apply emerging academic policies.
- Overall, it is highly recommended to give lighter weight to faculty members' student evaluations in order to allow students to also adjust to a learning environment that emphasizes academic integrity and is striving to be free from grade inflation.
- Furthermore, other potential grade inflation factors should be examined such as course drop rates (e.g. those who would have received lower grades withdraw from the course), any exceptions made for graduating students, and the approval of grade alterations.
- The faculty and the administration need to be clear from the beginning of the semester that earning an 'A' means that they need to produce a higher quality of work. The grading rubric needs to be clear to the students from the beginning of the semester. Perhaps it would be good to give them examples of what A, B, C, or D work represents. This way it will be clear to them.
- Students need to be reminded that their grade is reflective of achievement, not a gift. There seems to be a growing trend of "I'm paying to be here, so you should give me a good grade." Thus, private or public universities in the Middle East should investigate students' attitudes about their assessments.

CONCLUSION

Is there grade inflation at institutions in the Middle East? Since this is an extremely sensitive subject, it is important for quality assurance representatives and administrators to collaborate with different institutions to

investigate grade inflation in a culturally sensitive manner. Dealing with grade inflation is going to take courage (Cushman, 2003), planning and statistically sound methods. Administrators should conduct systematic research on this issue and publish their findings to fill a void of literature about Middle Eastern institutions.

Levine and Cureton (1998) point out that grade inflation has a negative affect on an undergraduate degree by diminishing its value. However, the effects of grade inflation cannot be blamed on any one particular aspect of the whole process. It is generally a result of the whole system being used and it should be assessed over a period of time. This could be detrimental to the higher education system in that if the grades are perceived as being inflated graduate schools as well as employers are more than likely to overlook the grades. This can cause graduate schools to focus on entrance exams for admittance. As for finding jobs upon graduating, those who will get the jobs are the ones who have connections and know how to network. The problem with this is that it can put others at a disadvantage especially if a person does not do well on exams or doesn't have any connections.

Although grade inflation has existed at some universities (especially at research or liberal arts institutions), students who work harder performed better across specific time periods (Kuh & Hu, 1999). Nevertheless, the issue has the potential to effect how institutions are perceived by employers and graduate schools. Future research should involve collecting faculty and students' perceptions of grade inflation and related issues to include Middle East institutions in this global debate.

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Appendix A: Academic Integrity Survey
(To be inserted)

Appendix A

Academic Policy Survey for Higher Education Institutions

The purpose of the following survey is to get your feedback on various academic policies that will influence quality assurance activities your institution.

A. Background

1. Which department do you belong to?	
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B. Grade Distributions: Do you believe the following factors contribute to students earning high grades at your institution?

1. Highest quiz grades used for assessment.	Yes	Somewhat	No
2. Bonus points on exams.	Yes	Somewhat	No
3. Extra credit assignments.	Yes	Somewhat	No
4. Student evaluations of teachers effect salary bonus.	Yes	Somewhat	No

5. Practice questions are the same, or similar, to exams.	Yes	Somewhat	No
6. High academic proficiency level of students.	Yes	Somewhat	No
7. Socioeconomic status of students.	Yes	Somewhat	No
8. Students attended private high schools.	Yes	Somewhat	No
9. High percentages assigned to each assessment.	Yes	Somewhat	No
10. Midterm assessment (70%) is too high.	Yes	Somewhat	No
11. Final exam assessment (30%) is too low.	Yes	Somewhat	No
12. Students repeating challenging courses.	Yes	Somewhat	No
13. Students know about exam questions from previous students.	Yes	Somewhat	No

14. If you were to increase the difficulty of your assessments, how would this effect your student evaluations? My ratings would... A. Decrease B. Increase C. Stay the Same

15. Do have any solutions for any of the above issues? Please note on the back of this sheet.

Thank You